

A MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE SCIENCE OF NUMERICAL METHODS THROUGH DIGITAL LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: This article talks about the importance of the formation of students' knowledge and skills through using digital educational technologies , the development of a model used in the educational process .

Basic phrases: modeling, expert model, artificial intelligence, platform, algorithm, assimilation.

It has been recognized by research scientists that the concept of the model of a future specialist should be understood as a generalized image of specialists in a certain field, reflecting the main characteristics of the object being studied.

Researcher N.F. Talyzina developed a general methodological approach to modeling the process of adequately preparing a future specialist for professional activity, and stated the following, emphasizing the need to reflect the expected result and the integral relationship of the ways to achieve it in this model : “The problem of the expert model occupies an important place in determining the content of educational programs as well as curricula” [1].

On the basis of the conducted scientific research, the knowledge, skills and competences of the general professional and specialized subjects, the methodology of their formation, and the program for the educational process, which should be mastered by the students in classroom training and independent education during the process of creative training of specialists in the field of mathematics and software of information systems for professional activity in general and specialized disciplines, the structural model of specialist training was developed in the process of using educational tools.

The improved model of the development of the science of “Numerical methods” based on digital educational technologies can be explained as follows:

This model envisages “training of competitive personnel in the field of mathematics and software of information systems by means of DTS and qualification requirements” as a social order. As a goal, attention is focused on “Improving the methodology of teaching general professional subjects with the help of digital educational technology tools”.

The tasks of the calendar-technological component include: study of methodological conditions, improvement of professional competence; theoretical and practical training process includes competence development in general professional subjects. In it, it is considered that the production of innovative technologies through artificial intelligence controlled without the human factor and their introduction into the educational system will serve the rise of emerging specialists.

Improving the content of the activity with the help of mobile applications, organizing remote circles and creating platforms for the subject “Numerical methods” taught in higher education institutions, using social networks to spend the free time of students productively and meaningfully, and to increase their interest in the subjects consists of gaining.

By carrying out the technological process of preparation for professional activity: lectures and practical training are formed using fully digital technologies; pre-prepared presentations, video lectures and animations are used for training; the materials prepared by the teacher are very important for the students to get a perfect education.

The training is aimed at a specific goal and is managed by the teacher, as a result of which skills and abilities are formed based on the knowledge obtained from the theoretical lessons necessary to perform a specific task. In independent education, students study the materials prepared by the teacher individually.

Blended learning, problem-based learning, Scarab and e-learning technologies were used in the educational process. Using the above-mentioned

technologies, problem situation, panel discussion, classic pairs, scaling, concept analysis, and the latest thought methods were applied to the educational process.

The result-evaluation component of our model assumes the presence of the following structural criteria: motivational (scientific evidence, the need to implement digital educational activities); cognitive (character development, education, scientific reasoning, software training tools, etc.); active (reflecting pedagogical, specific culture, subjective-national ideas and the goal set before it).

The defining features of the cognitive system are as follows: efficiency - focusing on solving practical problems quickly and efficiently; algorithmic - based on algorithms; assimilation - assimilation of the system as a result of learning; is flexibility.

In our model presented above, the process of student evaluation is carried out in accordance with the form of the lesson, based on clearly defined criteria. Evaluation criteria is an indicator that shows the degree to which the student has achieved educational goals, and determines the level of mastery by the teacher or digitalized teaching systems. Evaluation criteria are an indicator of the extent to which learning objectives have been achieved.

We describe these indicators using: “High” - 90-100 points, “Medium” - 71-89 points, “Low” medium -60-70 points.

Our research shows that the solutions to the above-mentioned problems should be provided to teachers to ensure that the digital technologies used in the lesson and different methods of knowledge diagnosis serve to further increase the efficiency of learning.

To sum up, in the process of studying the science of “Numerical methods”, students can learn the experiences of countries with high world rankings in the use of digital educational technologies in their future professional activities and the level of development in their fields (online and mobile through applications) serves for the development of our country.

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